

CESAER

The strong and united voice of universities
of science and technology in Europe

Continuity and Transition
Annual Report 2022

Table of Contents

02 | Letter from the President

04 | Foreword from the Secretary General

06 | Strong

07 | United

08 | Mission, Aims, Activities and Benefits

11 | Our Members

13 | Presidency and Board of Directors

14 | Areas of work

14 | Sustainability

15 | Openness of Science & Technology

16 | Learning & Teaching

17 | Innovation

18 | Benchmark

19 | Human Resources

20 | Sustainable Funding

21 | Resources

22 | Secretariat

Letter from the President

We started the year 2022 on a high note by welcoming five new Members, and the launch of our Work Plan 2022 to 2023 'Advance contribution of universities of S&T to knowledge societies for a sustainable future' with the establishment of seven task forces. This reinforced our ongoing efforts to inspire and support universities of science and technology (S&T) to continue releasing transformative forces to meet societal challenges, including boosting interdisciplinarity and safeguarding academic freedom.

These endeavours were cast in a new light in February with the invasion of Ukraine by Putin's regime. This brought the urgent need to promote peace and the rule of international law, while helping to build long-term bridges and alleviate suffering, sharply into focus. Following our association's swift condemnation of the invasion, we started a year-long period of (i) exploring ways in which our association and its leaders and experts can concretely contribute; while also (ii) sparking a value-based discussion on the role of universities of S&T. As S&T have played determining roles in conflicts and in science diplomacy, academics and academic institutions can have specific roles, including to build the frameworks needed. These trajectories are ongoing as we enter 2023, and we are proud to welcome the National Technical University of Ukraine 'Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute' as they join our association and contribute their valuable perspectives.

"... the invasion of Ukraine by Putin's regime... brought the urgent need to promote peace and the rule of international law, while helping to build long-term bridges and alleviate suffering, sharply into focus."

On behalf of my colleagues in the Board, we want to extend our gratitude to our envoys: Christian Lermينياux (ParisTech) and Vojtěch Petráček (Czech Technical University in Prague) our envoys to the French and Czech presidencies of the Council of the European Union (EU) during 2022, Anna Steiger (TU Wien) to Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA), Peter Elspass (*Leibniz Universität Hannover*) to the European Higher Education Sector Observatory and Karel Luyben (TU Delft) to the European Open Science Cloud. They continue to play a vital and visible role in our association's work.

We were also proud to again see evidence of high-level appointments from amongst our Members and their leaders, including through the nomination of our Director Elvira Fortunato as Portuguese Minister for Science, Technology and Higher Education and of the President of *Université Paris-Saclay* Sylvie Retailleau as the French Minister for Education, Research and Innovation. My final words of thanks go to our partners and friends, notably including the European University Association (EUA), the International Sustainable Campus Network (ISCN), Science Europe, and the Network of Universities in Capitals (UNICA) in the important ongoing work on sustainability and our joint event in the context of the United Nations Climate Change Conference COP27.

It was also a delight to again have our CESAER Annual Meetings in-person, this year hosted by *Technische Universität Dresden* (TU Dresden) to explore regional visions for global challenges in digital transformation. As we move through 2023, I look forward to continuing our important work together, with everyone from our Members, and with all our friends and partners, both online and in person.

Rik Van de Walle

President of CESAER

Rector of GHENT
UNIVERSITY

Foreword from the Secretary General

Building on the conceptual and methodological achievements from 2020 to 2021 concerning the contribution of universities of S&T to sustainability, over 1,550 volunteers and leaders of this association are making progress on this crucial agenda along a new biennial cycle until the end of 2023. Representatives of the Members joined forces and worked together in seven active and productive task forces: sustainability, openness of S&T, learning & teaching, innovation, benchmark, human resources and sustainable funding.

This association united fifty-eight Members from twenty-eight countries in Europe and beyond, with the (i) *Institut Polytechnique de Paris*, (ii) National Technical University of Athens, (iii) Sapienza University of Rome, (iv) Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava and (v) University of Southampton accepting the invitation to (re-) join as (new) Members by 1 January. In light of the invasion of Ukraine by Putin's regime and our corresponding condemnation, and following the publication of a statement in which the rector of Tomsk Polytechnic University (TPU) aligned with the Russian regime, the Board on 7 March unanimously suspended the membership of TPU with immediate effect. The Board judged that TPU had 'committed an infringement of the common values of the association resulting in the loss of mutual trust and confidence' in line with article 4.5 of the Articles of Association.

"... it has been an honour to serve as Secretary General of one of the most important and influential university associations for the past seven years."

We have commenced a new biennial term for the Presidency and Board, and the second term of President Rik Van de Walle. The resignation of four Directors obliged us to hold by-elections on 14 October to comply with the statutory requirement to have at least nine Directors. We have nearly reached our goal to have parity in gender representation in its governing bodies as the Board over the course of the last year has appointed five male and six female (Co-) Chairs of our task forces. As the General Assembly on 14 October elected Karine Samuel (*Université Grenoble-Alpes*), Justyna Szostak (GdanskTech) and Toril Hernes (Norwegian University of Science & Technology) as Directors 2023-2025, the Board is composed of six male and five female Directors.

On a more personal note, it has been an honour to serve as Secretary General of one of the most important and influential university associations for the past seven years. This network grew both internally, as it now reaches more staff at Member universities than ever before, and externally as its voice has become more impactful and widely recognised. I leave this post with a sense of achievement and lots of gratitude to the colleagues and friends from the Members, the Secretariat, the European institutions and our partners for the excellent cooperation over these past years.

I wish Mattias Björnmalm and his crew lots of success and all the best!

David Bohmert
Secretary General
CESAER (2016-22)

Strong

In 2022, we had

58

Members

in

28

countries

in Europe and
beyond, which:

Educated over

1.2m

students >

of which 227,230 are international

Employed over

69,670

academic staff

From 2017 to 2022,
our Members have secured a total of:

1,241 grants from the European Research Council ([ERC](#));

2,644 grants from Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions ([MSCA](#));

10,327 collaborative projects

with a collective combined value of over **€5 bn**

United

Over

1,500

staff from our Members were involved in our association as volunteers and leaders.

In the last year, we produced

15 publications

e.g. positions, white papers, open letters and statements.

In addition, staff from our Members (co-) authored

3 editorials & 8 op-eds

Mission, Aims, Activities and Benefits

Mission

Rooted in advanced engineering education and research, CESAER is an international association of leading specialised and comprehensive universities with a strong science and technology profile that advocate, learn from each other and inspire debates. Our Members champion excellence in higher education, training, research and innovation, contribute to knowledge societies for a sustainable future and deliver significant scientific, economic, social and societal impact.

The aims of the association are to:

- 1 Advocate Members' interests by aiding policymakers and funders shaping European strategies, policies and programmes for research, education, innovation and university leadership;
- 2 Learn from each other by sharing and spreading intelligence, knowledge and best practice in research, education, innovation and university leadership;
- 3 Safeguard sustainable funding by advocating and shaping sustainable competitive and non-competitive funding streams to our Members from different sources at various levels;
- 4 Lead debate on key issues by advancing reflection and understanding of the roles of science and technology in knowledge societies for a sustainable future;
- 5 Amplify the Members' and Association's strengths by supporting Members in displaying their excellence and distinctiveness in Europe and beyond.

Mission, Aims, Activities and Benefits

Activities:

The aims of the association will be achieved by the following activities:

- Monitor European strategies, policies and programmes and inform Members;
- Undertake consultations and surveys amongst Members and represent and advocate their collective interests;
- Publish inputs, positions, white papers and press releases;
- Liaise with European institutions and other stakeholders;
- Share experiences, identify best practice and provide guidance;
- Establish and empower committees, task forces and workgroups;
- Organise events, such as meetings, workshops and conferences;
- Support Members' communication and outreach activities in Europe and beyond;
- Engage with Members and encourage active participation in the work of the Association.

Mission, Aims, Activities and Benefits

Benefits

The aims of the association will be achieved by the following activities:

- A strong and united voice of universities of science and technology in Europe, taking into account a range of needs and positions;
- Collective and acknowledged representation, connections and advocacy on key issues such as the European Research, Education and Innovation Areas and the EU funding programmes to senior policymakers, politicians and funders at the heart of European decision-making;
- Privileged access to and exchange with leaders, experts and volunteers from leading universities of science and technology;
- Amplified efforts and impact at regional and national levels through international best practice by the collective of Members;
- Opportunities to set agendas, inspire and pave the way for developments directed towards shaping knowledge societies for a sustainable future;
- Support to positioning leaders and experts of Members at the European level;
- Access to intelligence and resources in the Extranet exclusively for Members;
- Participation in a range of bodies that strengthen Members' expertise in learning and teaching, excellent research and innovation, leadership, and strategic influence;
- Being part of a network of peer leading research-intensive universities of science and technology fostering and multiplying cooperation, including learning and teaching, excellent research and innovation, and infrastructures;
- Attractive range and programme of events such as CESAER Annual Meetings and workshops every year;
- Collective safeguarding of scientific integrity, academic freedom and institutional autonomy;
- Inclusive and respectful working environment that celebrates equality and diversity;
- Sharing of best practice and tailored benchmarking data between members from various data sources and surveys;
- Exclusive access to dedicated training sessions.

Our Members

Our Members

- | | | | |
|----|--|----|--|
| 1 | Aalborg University - Denmark | 32 | Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava - Slovakia |
| 2 | Aalto University - Finland | 33 | Tallinn University of Technology - Estonia |
| 3 | Brno University of Technology - Czechia | 34 | Technion - Israel Institute of Technology - Israel |
| 4 | Budapest University of Technology and Economics - Hungary | 35 | <i>Technische Universität Berlin</i> - Germany |
| 5 | Chalmers University of Technology - Sweden | 36 | <i>Technische Universität Braunschweig</i> - Germany |
| 6 | Czech Technical University in Prague - Czechia | 37 | <i>Technische Universität Darmstadt</i> - Germany |
| 7 | Delft University of Technology - Netherlands | 38 | <i>Technische Universität Dresden</i> - Germany |
| 8 | <i>Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne</i> - Switzerland | 39 | TU Wien - Austria |
| 9 | ETH Zurich - Switzerland | 40 | <i>Universidad Politécnica de Madrid</i> - Spain |
| 10 | Gdańsk University of Technology - Poland | 41 | <i>Universidade NOVA de Lisboa</i> - Portugal |
| 11 | Ghent University - Belgium | 42 | <i>Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya</i> - Spain |
| 12 | Graz University of Technology - Austria | 43 | <i>Universitat Politècnica de València</i> - Spain |
| 13 | <i>Institut National des Sciences Appliquées Lyon</i> - France | 44 | <i>Université Catholique de Louvain</i> - Belgium |
| 14 | <i>Institut Polytechnique de Paris</i> - France | 45 | <i>Université Grenoble Alpes</i> - France |
| 15 | <i>Instituto Superior Técnico</i> - Portugal | 46 | <i>Université Paris-Saclay</i> - France |
| 16 | Istanbul Technical University - Turkey | 47 | University College Dublin - Ireland |
| 17 | Karlsruhe Institute of Technology - Germany | 48 | University of Belgrade - Serbia |
| 18 | Kaunas University of Technology - Lithuania | 49 | University of Porto - Portugal |
| 19 | KTH Royal Institute of Technology - Sweden | 50 | University of Sheffield - United Kingdom |
| 20 | KU Leuven - Belgium | 51 | University of Southampton - United Kingdom |
| 21 | <i>Leibniz Universität Hannover</i> - Germany | 52 | University of Strathclyde - United Kingdom |
| 22 | Lund University - Sweden | 53 | University of Stuttgart - Germany |
| 23 | National Technical University of Athens - Greece | 54 | University of Surrey - United Kingdom |
| 24 | Norwegian University of Science and Technology - Norway | 55 | University of Twente - Netherlands |
| 25 | ParisTech - France | 56 | University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest - Romania |
| 26 | <i>Politecnico di Milano</i> - Italy | 57 | Warsaw University of Technology - Poland |
| 27 | <i>Politecnico di Torino</i> - Italy | | |
| 28 | Poznan University of Technology - Poland | | |
| 29 | Riga Technical University - Latvia | | |
| 30 | RWTH Aachen University - Germany | | |
| 31 | Sapienza University of Rome - Italy | | |

Presidency and Board of Directors

Presidency

Rik Van de Walle
President
Rector of Ghent University

Mihnea Costoiu
Vice President
Rector of the University
POLITEHNICA of Bucharest

Jennifer Herek
Vice President & Treasurer
Dean of Faculty of S&T at
University of Twente

On top of the Presidency, we had the following Directors:

Tim Bedford
Associate Principal Research &
Knowledge Exchange of University
of Strathclyde

Elvira Fortunato
Vice Rector of *Universidade NOVA
de Lisboa*
(resigned in March 2022)

Toril Hernes
Vice President of Innovation at
Norwegian University of Science
and Technology

Olga Mazurina
Rector's Delegate for International
Affairs at Tomsk University of
Technology
(resigned in March 2022)

Mikael Östling
Deputy President of KTH Royal
Institute of Technology

Henrik Pedersen
Dean of Faculty of IT & Design at
Aalborg University
(resigned in October 2022)

Guillermo Cisneros Perez
Rector of *Universidad Politécnica
de Madrid*

Karine Samuel
Vice President for International
Affairs of *Université Grenoble Alpes*

Anna Andrea Steiger
Vice Rector for Human Resources
& Gender of TU Wien

Justyna Szostak
Chair of Internationalisation
Committee at Gdańsk University of
Technology

Ronald Tetzlaff
Chief Technology Officer &
Internationalisation at *Technische
Universität Dresden*

Roberto Zanino
Rector's Delegate for European
Relations at *Politecnico di Torino*

Marc Zolver
Vice President for International
Affairs of *Centrale Supélec,
Université Paris-Saclay*
(resigned in September 2022)

Areas of work:

Sustainability

The [Task Force Sustainability](#) focused its efforts around three themes: (i) inspire our Members and other universities of S&T about their contribution to knowledge societies for a sustainable future, (ii) advocate the corresponding framework conditions for optimising the contribution of universities of S&T to policy makers and funders, and (iii) learn from each other and promote best practice when contributing to knowledge societies for a sustainable future.

The task force released a [joint report](#) together with ISCN, Science Europe and the University of Strathclyde (April) to reiterate our engagement to the [Call to Action](#) and our commitment to continue our cooperation. Together with these partners, the task force organised a session '[Engaging Researchers for the Net-Zero Transition](#)' at the EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF) 2022 in July, at which the task force Chair, Guillermo Cisneros Pérez (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid) and previous Chair of the Workgroup Sustainability 2020-2021, Mikael Östling (KTH), both contributed. The task force held regular meetings with key partners to discuss seeking new signatories for the Call to Action, and organised a follow-up conference on 3 November on '[interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition](#)'. This took stock of progress made towards the Call to Action with new partners EUA and UNICA.

To carry out the work from the previous work plan, the task force established a writers team which has been meeting regularly to advance and finalise the white paper and declaration on the contribution of universities of S&T to sustainability (due in October 2023). As part of these efforts, the task force launched a series of questions to consult our Members on the challenges they face and on their contribution to sustainability. In October, Guillermo Cisneros Pérez presented the results of the consultation during a dedicated workshop on 'disruptive innovation for a sustainable future' that brought together experts on sustainability and disruptive innovation.

Impact Story: Call to Action and net-zero global partnership

Our association launched and is a leader of a global effort around science for the net-zero transition also in the context of the United Nations Climate Change Conference, together with the International Sustainable Campus Network (ISCN), Science Europe and the University of Strathclyde.

“Addressing global climate change requires global collaboration, and science and technology is an important part of the solution. Specifically, research and education communities have a crucial role to play in delivering net-zero, and our Call to Action sparked a global joint venture with partners from Hong Kong to Cape Town to Mexico City. We have created a unique platform where universities, research organisations and funders are engaging towards the net-zero transition. Only together can we fight climate change and we look forward to advancing with our global partners.”

Director and Co-Chair of Task Force Innovation Tim Bedford (Associate Principal for Research and Innovation at the University of Strathclyde

Openness of Science & Technology

The [Task Force Openness of Science & Technology](#) focused its efforts around three themes: (i) open science, (ii) knowledge safety and security and (iii) citizen science. For the open science theme, the task force [coordinated the delivery](#) of two white papers [Successful implementation of Open Access strategies at Universities of S&T](#) (April) and [Open Access and conference papers in engineering disciplines](#) (April), and provided advice to our Board who [endorsed the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#) (April). As part of the follow-up work, its Co-Chair Simone Rehm gave a presentation as an invited contributor to a session at [ESOF 2022](#) in July. The task force contributed to preparing joint statements on [Scientific knowledge must be protected to ensure a Europe fit for the digital age](#) (January) and [Support for educational and scientific exemptions from the Digital Services Act](#) (April). For the knowledge safety and security theme, task force members contributed to a series of workshops feeding into the drafting of the position [‘Four guiding principles for the Global Framework for S&T Cooperation’](#) (April).

For the citizen science theme, the task force supported the finalisation of a joint conference statement together with the UK Royal Academy of Engineering on [‘Key Technologies Shaping the Future: Foresight and strategic recommendations’](#). A subgroup was also formed to explore effective two-way engagement between our Members and society at large, in order to create a shared understanding around the roles of key technologies (e.g. artificial intelligence and quantum technology). The task force supported Karel Luyben (TU Delft) as our European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Envoy and [President of the EOSC Association](#), as well as [Katharina Eggenberger](#) (ETH Zurich) and [Sally Chambers](#) (Ghent University) as our association’s Envoys to the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Stakeholders Forum.

The task force also contributed to the drafting of the [position](#) ‘Scientific & technological infrastructures to help tackle local and global challenges’. Simone Rehm (University of Stuttgart) and Jennifer Herek (University of Twente) co-chaired this task force, and Ina Schneider (University of Stuttgart) and Irna van der Molen (University of Twente) acted as its co-secretaries uniting experts and leaders in European research policies, open science, knowledge safety & export control and citizen science, outreach and engagement.

Impact Story: European Open Science Cloud

Our EOSC Envoy Karel Luyben was elected President of [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), Association which leads on the strategic development and implementation of EOSC. The EOSC has been granted special status as a co-programmed European Partnership under Horizon Europe, which will fortify EOSC with European funding of almost €1 billion, including in-kind contributions of €500 million.

“I thank CESAER for its continued trust and for nominating me for re-election, and it was truly an honour to receive the support from the EOSC community to be [elected](#) to serve a second term as President of the EOSC Association. The next phase for the community now will be to boost the roll-out and expansion of a ‘Minimum Viable EOSC’ which is bringing value to users, such as researchers, beyond their current use of infrastructure and services, thus helping to fully bring EOSC to life. Without the support of associations such as CESAER, EOSC would not be where it is today, demonstrating the type of positive impact we can have together.”

[EOSC Envoy Karel Luyben \(Rector Magnificus Emeritus of TU Delft\)](#)

Learning & Teaching

The [Task Force Learning & Teaching](#) (i) advocated to shape European education policies and strategies, working together closely with the [Task Force Sustainable Funding](#), (ii) explored the 'engineer of the future, and (iii) worked on a successor of the [Competition Best Idea 2021](#). The task force led our contributions to the European Strategy for Universities. Key deliverables concerned the [position](#) 'Advancing the flagship initiatives of the European Strategy for Universities' (28 March) and its support to the engagement of our Members in European University alliances. Marc Zolver from Université Paris-Saclay, succeeded by [Justyna Szostak](#) from Gdansk Tech and Roberto Zanino from Politecnico di Torino, co-chaired this task force uniting experts and leaders in learning & teaching.

Impact Story: European Research Area

Our association was invited to the [ERA Forum](#) which advanced the European Research Area, including through our association's [concrete contributions](#).

"Following intense efforts during 2021, including statements in [April](#) and [October](#), we were pleased to contribute to the set-up of the [ERA University associations group](#) and be invited to be 'at the table' of the European Research Area (ERA) Forum together with the European Commission, Council of the EU and member states. Ensuring the full engagement of associations such as ours in this context has been a big win-win for all sides, illustrating the type of clear and positive impact you can have by being a constructive and trusted partner to shape key policy areas."

Mattias Björnmalm, Secretary General

Innovation

The [Task Force Innovation](#) (i) supports the development of sustainable innovation ecosystems in and around universities of S&T, (ii) advocates to shape European innovation policies and EU funding instruments in collaboration with the Task Force Sustainable Funding, (iii) explores the evolving model of engagement of PhD candidates at universities of S&T with non-academic partners and (iv) works together with the Task Force Openness of S&T on innovation aspects of global S&T cooperation and engagement and ensuring suitable balance between 'open and closed' also with non-academic partners.

The task force published the [position](#) 'Boosting disruptive innovation by fostering new mindsets and co-creating innovation' (May), and presented it at the Week of Innovative Regions in Europe conference 2022.

The task force also contributed to the work on Knowledge Valorisation related to Action 7 of the European Research Area (ERA) policy agenda. Our advisor Louise Drogoul, together with Co-Chair Tim Bedford (University of Strathclyde), represented our association in the online community of practice, launched by the European Commission and contributed to the development of the [Code of Practice](#) for the smart use of intellectual property. It also submitted input on [Guiding Principles for Knowledge Valorisation](#) (April). Complementing these efforts, the task force most recently (December) contributed to the delivery of the [position](#) 'Advancing innovation and knowledge valorisation from European Innovation Council'.

On the models of engagement of PhD candidates with non-academic partners, the task force has established a team to debate and discuss the issue further. The team will run a workshop in order to launch a survey and summarise all their findings in a report.

This task force is co-chaired by Toril Hernes (Norwegian University of Science and Technology) and Tim Bedford (University of Strathclyde), Yvonne Kinnaird (University of Strathclyde) acts as its Secretary. It unites experts in innovation, specialists and coordinators of academia and non-academia relations and university leaders.

Photo: Task Force Innovation meeting in Rome

Benchmark

The [Task Force Benchmark](#) (i) promoted the integration of next generation and progressive metrics for institutional development, and promotes FAIR and open data; (ii) contributed to the development and design of European Higher Education Sector Observatory; and (iii) [observed](#) university rankings, especially changes in rankings methodology, engaged with rankers, provided structured feedback to them and shared experiences among Members. A key deliverable concerned the [position](#) 'Design principles for European Higher Education Sector Observatory', which offers five principles for the design and development of this observatory (8 June).

Our Board [appointed](#) Peter Elspass (Leibniz Universität Hannover) as our association's European Higher Education Sector Observatory Envoy to support the effective follow-up of the position, and the task force supports him in this appointment. Peter chaired this task force uniting (senior) experts in institutional research and managers of strategy and institutional policy from our Members.

Human Resources

The [Task Force Human Resources](#) focused its efforts on three themes: (i) digital transformation in HR, (ii) supporting diverse and modern academic careers and (iii) achieving the [Equality, Diversity and Inclusion \(EDI\) Pledges](#). For the digital transformation theme, the task force hosted workshops on digitalisation strategies of our Members, and on the '[Vienna Manifesto on Digital Humanism](#)' (June). For the theme of academic careers, the task force supported Mattias Björnmalm (Secretariat) representing our association in the [core group](#) of the coalition on reforming research assessment.

The task force organised a [joint workshop](#) 'evolving academic assessment together with [DORA](#)' (April), resulting in a [workbook](#) to be used with the [SPACE rubric](#). The task force also provided advice to our Board of Directors who decided for our association to [sign](#) the 'Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment' and appoint Anna Steiger as our association's [COARA Envoy](#). For the EDI theme, the task force continued the successful organisation of [EDI.Labs](#) where our Members share good practices for supporting equality, diversity and inclusion. This task force unites experts and leaders in human resources from our Members, and was chaired by Anna Steiger (TU Wien) with Silvia Rauscher (TU Wien) as its Secretary.

Impact Story: Research assessment

Our association was invited to the [core group](#) which shaped the agreement on research assessment.

“Supporting diverse and modern academic careers goes to the heart of what our Members do, and ensuring suitable research assessment practices is an important lever. The work of our association in this area is therefore vital, and I am proud that our association has been and remains deeply involved in the process: from being invited to the core group which contributed to the drafting of the agreement, to the Board of Directors [deciding](#) to sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, and now in the follow-up with [COARA](#). Being part of shaping these important developments at the European level showcases the impact we can have together in associations such as CESAER, by being proactive, visible and constructive partners at the European level and beyond.”

[COARA](#) Envoy Anna Steiger (Vice Rector at TU Wien)

Sustainable Funding

The [Task Force Sustainable Funding](#) (i) advocated for sustainable funding and its vital importance for delivering long-term impact and to safeguard the balance between (top-down) challenge-driven research and (bottom-up) investigator-driven frontier research; (ii) advocated to shape European research, education and innovation policies and strategies (especially towards the EU institutions), and contribute to implementing the ERA and the European Education Area (EEA); and (iii) helped shape EU funding programmes in research, education and innovation such as Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF).

The task force contributed to key deliverables, including by publishing positions and statements related to [Europe fit for the digital age](#) (January), [European Strategy for Universities](#) (March), [Digital Services Act](#) (April), and the Contributions of universities of science & technology to implement the European Research Area (June), [Boost synergies in research and innovation funding](#) (October) and [Provide clarity on DNSH to boost contributions of science & technology](#).

The task force supported [Vojtěch Petráček](#) (Rector of Czech Technical University in Prague) and [Stefan Bengtsson](#) (President of Chalmers University of Technology) as our association's envoys towards the Czech and Swedish Presidencies of the Council of the EU, respectively. Christian Gerhardt (TU Dresden) and Wendy Sonneveld (Ghent University) co-chaired this task force, and Romy Ginzel (TU Dresden) acted as its Secretary. The task force united experts and managers on research, education and innovation funding instruments, and on international and EU affairs, from our Members.

Impact Story: Infrastructures and synergies

Following a meeting, hosted at the Czech Technical University of Prague (CTU Prague) in summer 2022 between the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU and our Board of Directors, our association provided its support to help advance the key priority areas of infrastructures and funding synergies.

“We warmly welcomed the priorities of the Czech Presidency on infrastructures and synergies. These areas are interconnected and foundational for universities of S&T to deliver the highest quality and impact in research, innovation and education. We engaged closely with our friends in the EU institutions and in the Presidency, resulting in two [positions](#) which also outline our commitments, expertise and experience to help advance these key areas. I am grateful to our task forces which helped in the development of these positions, as connecting leading experts at the content level with the highest political levels clearly helps to amplify our impact.”

[Envoy to the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU, Vojtěch Petráček \(Rector of CTU Prague\)](#)

Resources

The annual subscription in 2022 amounted to €12,000. The annual account for our fiscal year from 1 October 2021 to 30 September 2022 was:

TYPE OF COSTS	ACCOUNT 2021-2022 (TO THE NEAREST €1,000)
INTERNAL BODIES	26,000
SECRETARIAT	67,000
EVENTS	1,000
INITIATIVES	51,000
ICT	12,000
ADMINISTRATION	10,000
SALARIES	448,000

TOTAL EXPENSES	615,000
TOTAL INCOME	672,000
TO RESERVE	57,000

Secretariat

Indrė Antanavičiūtė
Operations Manager

Mattias Björnmalm
Secretary General

Louise Drogoul
Advisor for Innovation & Sustainability

Sophie Ratcliff
Junior Advisor for Higher Education

The Secretariat ensures the execution and implementation of the decisions by the General Assembly, the Board and the Presidency and manages and supports the daily operation of the association. The Secretariat supports our over 1,550 volunteers and leaders.

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of science and technology in Europe

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